

Relation between moral judgment and the perception of moral injury in medical trainee

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Abstract

Introduction: Moral injury is an emotional wound secondary to exposure to traumatic events. Medical trainees may be more vulnerable to its emotional and moral consequences. This study seeks to analyze the relationship between moral judgment and the perception of moral injury in medical trainees in the final years of their careers.

Methodology: A cross-sectional pilot study was performed on medical trainees in the tenth semester of their degree. The instruments used were the Moral Competence Test by George Lind and the de Moral Injury Scale Symptom—Healthcare Professionals. Data was analyzed using non-parametric tests.

Results: Most participants were female (77.8%), with a mean age of 22.4 years old. Females had a better average score on the moral judgment competence test, measured by the C-index ($p = 0.285$), but no statistically significant difference. On the other hand, physician had a higher C-index on the worker dilemma ($p < 0.001$). However, changes in C-Index did not significantly affect moral injury ($p = 0.6325$).

Discussion/Conclusion: There is no significant correlation between moral injury and C-index. “Moral segmentation” was not evidenced in our sample, unlike other studies on Hispanic medical trainee. Due to the small and homogenous sample, results may not represent the medical trainee population. Future research should further explore this association to provide a better understanding of moral injury in medical trainees, particularly in Latin America.

Keywords Mesh: Ethics, Medical; Medical Staff; Moral Development; Psychological Distress

Introduction

Morality is the principles, norms, and values that lead human behavior and portray what is considered correct in society. According to Lickona, an individual's moral character is built by three aspects: knowledge, moral will, and moral actions, which are founded on habits and values present in daily life (1). On the other hand, ethical reasoning, according to Kohlberg, lies mainly in the values of justice, equality, and equity (2).

Medical practice often involves managing ethical dilemmas that test the moral judgment of health workers (3). When these ethical dilemmas are associated with the inability to prevent, witness, or perpetuate an act that transgresses the individual's moral values, it is considered a potentially morally injurious event (4). For this reason, health professionals are constantly at high risk of moral injury.

The concept of "moral injury" was first used by Vietnam War veterans in the context of post-traumatic stress disorder (3). Although moral injury has been typically associated with exceptional circumstances (i.e., war), it has recently been recognized in other contexts. According to Shay, to consider a situation morally injurious, there must be a betrayal of what is ethically correct by someone who has legitimate authority in a high-stakes situation (5). Moreover, moral injury is conceptually defined as a deep emotional wound that can be inflicted on an individual when witnessing situations of intense human suffering (3).

Multiple tools have been created to evaluate the moral competence of individuals, as they can deteriorate when an individual suffers from moral injury. George Lind's Moral Competence Test (MCT) evaluates morality from two perspectives: moral attitudes, which represent the individual's position when facing a moral dilemma, and moral competence, understood according to Kohlberg, as the ability to make moral decisions and judgments and act by such judgments (6). The numeric result of the MCT indicator is the C-Index (CI), which represents the degree of moral competence of individuals when their principles are put into practice in moral dilemmas posed by the MCT (7). A low IC implies that the individual only gives value to people who share their opinion. At the same time, a high IC means that the individual evaluates arguments based on their ethical quality even when they contradict their personal views (7).

There is a growing need to develop adequate moral competencies in medical practice. The relationship between the learning environment and moral development has been previously explored. Studies of medical trainees using MCT have demonstrated that moral attitudes remain stable throughout the semester. Still, moral competence appears to decline, with physicians in their final year of medical school scoring lower CI scores than first-year physician (mean CI 45.6 vs. 46.4) (8). This phenomenon is known as "moral regression," associated with educational opportunities lacking ethical and moral training (9). Different theories have been developed to explain this phenomenon. Medical schools have poor moral and ethical training due to the importance of technical training, such as the situation in Brazil or the highly competitive environment and poor relationship with professors, as seen in Germany (10,11).

However, Hispanic physicians' moral competence seems to vary according to the type of dilemma on the MJT, a trend called "moral segmentation." This segmentation reflects social

agents' influence on individuals from Hispanic cultures, mainly due to religion and military institutions rather than mere individual competence (12).

On the other hand, moral injury is a common phenomenon for medical trainees. It may appear in emergency wards when witnessing events that challenge one's moral code or traumatic events, such as acts of violence or restrictions on a patient's autonomy. Unlike professional healthcare providers, physicians view senior colleagues and professors as less accessible, hindering the opportunities to talk about their experiences (13).

Moral injury has been shown to have adverse effects on the mental health of medical trainees and affect clinical decision-making, occupational well-being, and the quality of medical care. Medical trainees may be at greater risk of suffering the consequences of moral injury as they have less experience dealing with suffering and fewer resources to manage their emotions (13). However, there are few studies evaluating moral injury in this population. Even when using similar terms, such as moral distress, the literature remains limited, especially in the Latin American context (14).

Moral injury affects medical' emotional well-being, compromises the quality of service, and contributes to burnout. In the Colombian case, the health system's challenges, including high workload, scarce resources, and the hierarchical structure of medical institutions, can intensify these effects (14).

Although moral judgment in medical trainees and its relationship with the academic level has been described, its correlation with moral injury has not been studied. Therefore, the objective of this pilot study is to analyze the relationship between moral judgment, according to George Lind's Moral Judgment Theory, and the perception of moral injury in medical trainees in the final year of their degree. In this pilot phase, we will only evaluate physicians from the last year of a Colombian university.

Methodology

Study design

A cross-sectional pilot study was conducted with non-probabilistic convenience sampling. The sample was collected using the "snowball" method. This study accomplished the ethical standards established by the Declaration of Helsinki of 2013. We follow article 11 of resolution 8430 of 1993 of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Colombia, because no intervention or intentional modification of the biological, physiological, psychological or social variables of the individuals participating in the study is carried out; this research is without risk. All participants gave their informed consent before filling out the questionnaire.

Participants

Sixty-three medical trainees, who were in the tenth semester of their degree, were included. Men and women between 21 and 31 years of age. Exclusion criteria included individuals with

neurocognitive disorders and/or cognitive disabilities that would prevent them from completing the survey.

Procedure

The survey was responded by physician last year. It was spread through social networks using an introductory infographic that exclusively invited medical trainees and gave basic information about the study. Before answering the survey, participants were presented with a summary of the study's purpose and informed consent. After answering the survey, the participants' scores were sent to their email, and a brief explanation of their results was provided.

Instruments

George Lind created the MCT to provide an objective measure of moral competence and moral attitudes in a simultaneous matter (12). This instrument, in its standard version, provides two short stories: a worker who breaks the law and a doctor who faces a situation in which he must decide whether to comply with the wish of a terminally ill woman to end her life; both represent a moral dilemma for the participant (15). Once the dilemma is presented, the participant must answer whether he agrees or disagrees with the conduct of the doctor and the worker and then express his degree of agreement on a scale from "+4" (agree) to "-4" (completely disagree) with six arguments on favor and against the final decision of each dilemma (15).

The IC is based on the total analysis derived from the pattern of the respondent's answers. This index is responsible for evaluating the different aspects of the respondent's responses: first, whether the score given to the argument was for its moral qualities or second, whether the score given was for the degree of agreement between the respondent's opinion and the nature of the argument (15). The result of the CI varies in a range of 0-100, where the respondent only agrees with the arguments that align with his opinion and when the respondent gives value to the argument only based on its quality, respectively. The CI is classified as low, 1-9; medium, 10 to 29; high, 30 to 49; and very high, more than 50 points according to the final score obtained (9,16). The C-score was calculated using the statistical procedure ANOVA based on the hypothesis that the internal variations in a group are similar because individuals in that group are similar per se (7,17).

The Moral Injury Symptom Scale-Healthcare Professional (MISS-HP) was developed to assess moral injury in healthcare professionals and clinical researchers (18). It is a ten-item scale that measures three dimensions: guilt and shame, spiritual problems, and condemnation. Responses are given using a 10-point Likert scale, which ranges from 1 (*strongly disagree*), 2-4 (mildly disagree), 5-6 (neutral), 7-9 (mildly agree), to 10 (*strongly agree*). The scores on each item are summed to obtain a total score varying from 10 to 100, where higher scores suggest a more significant presence of moral injury. Specifically, a score of 36 or higher indicates significant moral injury. The validated version of the MISS-HP in Spanish excludes the original items 1, 5, and 7, leaving a seven-item scale (19).

Statistical Analysis

Demographic factors were analyzed using descriptive measures, such as absolute and relative frequencies for qualitative (sex, age groups) variables and measures of central tendency for the quantitative variables (C Index, MISS-HP Score). An analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed to assess the influence of age groups (ANOVA) and sex (on Way ANOVA) on moral competencies and moral injury. The Shapiro-Wilk Test was used to evaluate the normal distribution of the data. Since the data was not normally distributed, the correlation between moral competence (C-Index) and moral injury (MISS-HP Score) was evaluated using Spearman's rank correlation. The comparison between both dilemmas was done using the Wilcoxon test due to the distribution of data. The significance level was set at 5%. All analyses were performed using R software.

Results

A total of 63 participants were included in the analysis. The demographic characteristics of the population are found in Table 1. Most of the participants were female (77.8%), compared to males (22.2%). The age ranged between 21 and 31 years old, with a mean of 22.4. Most participants were 22 years old, representing 58.7% of the population. The age distribution is slightly right-skewed due to a few older individuals (24, 26, and 31 years), with a standard deviation of approximately 1.37 years, indicating a limited dispersion around the mean. According to their current semester, all participants reported having completed 5 years of study. The mean score for moral injury was 31.698, and the mean CI score was 16.456.

Table 1. Population characteristics

Variables		Frequency (n)	Total (%)	Accumulated (%)
Sex	Female	49	77.8	77.8
	Male	14	22.2	100
Age	21	5	7.9	7.9
	22	37	58.7	66.7
	23	18	28.6	95.2
	24	1	1.6	96.8
	26	1	1.6	98.4
	31	1	1.6	100

For moral judgement competence, there was a significant difference between females and males, with females tending to perform better than males. Even so, there was no difference in moral injury according to sex, with neither group having significant symptoms of moral injury (Table 2).

Table 2: Influence of sex on moral judgment competence (C-Index) and moral injury

	Sex	Mean	SE	P-value ¹
C-Index	Female	17.57	2923.2	0.0285*
	Male	12.55		
MISS-HP Score	Female	31.65	5219	0.946
	Male	31.86		

¹ ANOVA, * Statistically significant

Age's influence on moral judgment competence and moral injury was not statistically significant (Table 3). When the physicians were grouped by age, younger physician tended to score higher CI scores without statistically significant differences. However, this tendency was not seen with moral injury.

Table 3: Influence of age on moral judgment competence (C-Index) and moral injury(MISS-HP Score)

	Age	Mean	SE	P-value ¹
C-Index	20-22	17.09	2923.2	0.3365
	23-24	16.13		
	25-26	11.37		
	>27	0.68		
MISS-HP Score	20-22	30.85	5219	0.700
	23-24	33.26		
	25-26	25		
	>27	44		

¹ ANOVA

The assessment of the physician's performance according to the moral dilemma showed a statistically significant difference between the CI scores (Table 4). The median CI score is greater in the worker dilemma than in the doctor dilemma, showing that medical trainees perform better in argument judgment when it does not involve a healthcare dilemma (Figure 1).

Table 4: Physician's performance according to the type of dilemma

	Mean	SD ¹	95% CI ² Mean Upper	95% CI ² Mean Lower	P-value ³
Total C-Index	16.456	7.527	18.274	14.498	<0.001*
C-Index Doctor	12.497	7.606	14.361	10.701	0.007*
C-Index Worker	18.033	6.233	19.504	16.490	<0.001*

¹ Standard Deviation, ² Confidence Interval, ³ Shapiro Wilk Test, * Statistically significant

Figure 1: Comparison between dilemmas: Worker vs Doctor dilemma (Wilcoxon Test)

Spearman's rank correlation demonstrated a weak correlation between moral judgment and moral injury ($\rho = -0.0614$) and was not statistically significant ($p = 0.6325$). The scatter plot that shows this relationship illustrates the weak correlation between CI scores and moral injury, as seen by the almost flat regression line (Figure 2). We expect the regression line to slope upward if there is a strong positive correlation. If there were a strong negative correlation, the line would slope downward. Since the line is nearly horizontal, it suggests that changes in CI do not significantly affect moral injury. The data points are also widely scattered, indicating high variability and reinforcing the weak relationship.

Figure 2: Correlation between moral judgment competence (C-Index) and moral injury

The same phenomenon occurred when correlating moral judgment based on dilemma with moral injury. The Spearman's rank correlation showed a weak correlation ($\rho = -0.201$) between the doctor dilemma and moral injury, which was not significant ($p = 0.1141$), as well as with the worker dilemma, with a weak ($\rho = -0.0428$) and non-significant ($p = 0.7385$)

correlation. The scatter plot shows dispersed data on both dilemmas, with a nearly horizontal regression line indicating the association is not statistically significant (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Correlation between moral judgment according to moral dilemma (C-Doctor and C-worker) and moral injury

Discussion

This pilot study sought to analyze the relationship between moral judgment competence and the perception of moral injury in medical trainees in the tenth semester of their degree. We found that moral judgment competence, measured by the CI score, was not associated with moral injury, even when evaluating the CI based on the moral dilemma. Age and sex were not associated with moral injury, but sex was statistically associated with CI (0.0285). Additionally, physician performed statistically significantly better on the worker dilemma ($p < 0.001$). Therefore, with this study, we intend to deepen our current knowledge of the effects of moral injury in medical education to reduce its consequences on moral development and foster the design of investigations on this topic in Latin America.

This pilot study is the first one to aim to find a correlation between moral injury and CI from the MCT. In our results, Spearman's rank showed a weak correlation between moral injury and CI, which means that the grade of moral injury does not affect the individual's capacity to judge arguments in favor or against a moral dilemma. Nonetheless, we cannot ensure that this result is representative of the medical trainee population.

On the other hand, this study shows that medical trainees from the tenth semester do not have significant symptoms of moral injury (mean = 31.698) because, according to the MISS-HP, participants must have a score equal to or greater than 36 (18) them to be considered with moral injury. According to a systematic review studying moral injury in healthcare clinicians, there is a lack of theoretical orientation over the moral injury concept. This leads to the belief that moral injury in healthcare practice is still in the early stages of research (20). Overall,

various associations have been described between moral injury and elements in the healthcare environment; for instance, morally injurious events often occur when a power imbalance is present (20). This power imbalance is mainly present in medical trainees and trainees because they are still just learning how to practice medicine and have less power to make decisions.

The present study did not find statistically significant differences in the CI when analyzed by age, with a slightly better performance in the group range from 20-22 years old. Similar studies have been conducted; for instance, a study using the MCT in medical trainees from Mexico found a mean CI score of 15.249, which is classified as medium moral competence according to Cohen, which is consistent with the findings of our study (21). They also found that CI scores were proportional to the participant's age, meaning lower CI in younger participants (21). A study conducted with medical trainees from Brazil and Portugal described a statistically significant negative correlation between age and moral competence, where the oldest physician showed lower CI scores (15). Given the discrepancy in the results presented by these studies and our own, the influence age has on the moral competence of medical trainees cannot be warranted.

Sex differences were significant for the moral competence judgment, where females scored higher CI scores (mean = 17.57) than males (mean = 12.55). However, mean CI scores for both sexes are classified as medium according to Cohen's parameters (16). Hence, even though there are numerical differences, moral judgment competence remains equal between the sexes. Studies evaluating this association have been subject to great controversy. Some studies have not found statistically significant differences (22,23), while others have (24,25). For example, in the Hispanic context, no differences have been found (15), and some studies have even found higher results in males (26). Differences in moral reasoning based on gender have been explored. Gilligan argued in her Theory of Moral Orientations that, even though care and justice are prevalent in both women and men, women tend to be more concerned with care and social relationships (27,28). Regardless, hormone levels, mainly testosterone and oxytocin, have been shown to influence females' responses to moral dilemmas toward more altruistic and utilitarian decisions (29).

Moral segmentation was not present in our population despite the statistically significant differences between CI scores in the doctor dilemma (mean = 12.497) and the worker dilemma (mean = 18.033). Moral segmentation is a phenomenon previously described in other investigations, where it can only be present when the CI calculated for each dilemma separately varies ≥ 8 (30). It is more prevalent in physician in the last year of their training, which has been explained by Hegazi due to the acquisition of moral concepts stage by stage during their medical training that affect moral judgment in specific contexts (30). Other studies have explained this phenomenon with the Dynamic Systems Theory, where the physician consolidate their moral judgment with self-authorship (ability to define beliefs, identity, and social relationships) (31). Even though moral segmentation is widely described in scientific literature, it was not evidenced in our findings. This can be possibly explained by the homogenous and small nature of our sample, without excluding the possibility of finding this phenomenon when analyzing more representative samples of our population.

This study provides valuable insights into the relationship between moral judgment and moral injury in medical trainees, a topic that has received limited attention in academic literature, particularly in Latin America. This study has several strengths; it addresses a crucial gap in understanding moral injury in medical trainees, offering empirical data that may contribute to improvements in the medical curriculum. The cross-sectional design allowed an initial exploration of associations between moral judgment and moral injury. The study employed well-established measurement tools, such as the MCT and the MISS-HP, which have been used in diverse populations in other studies (22,32).

The present study design is limited, with a small sample size of only 63 medical trainees. Since it is a pilot study, physicians are from the same university and training level. Hence, the sample is very homogeneous, hindering the process of drawing conclusions. Using convenience and snowball sampling may introduce selection bias, limiting the sample's representativeness and generalizability of its findings. Also, the study has a cross-sectional design that captures only a snapshot of moral judgment and moral injury, preventing causal inferences. Thus, a longitudinal approach could be performed to provide better insights into how moral injury evolves among medical trainees.

Future research should explore the progression of moral injury across different years of medical training using longitudinal studies to identify critical periods for interventions. The population could be expanded to multiple universities to include physicians from different medical training levels, backgrounds, and healthcare systems. Further research should be carried out in Latin American populations to explore the concept of "moral segmentation" and the cultural factors predisposing to its appearance. The influence of other factors on moral judgment and moral injury, such as emotional intelligence, empathy, or resilience, could also be analyzed. Addressing moral injury in medical education is important since it could lead to improved mental health outcomes for physicians and ultimately enhance the quality of patient care.

Conclusion

This pilot study allowed an initial exploration of the associations between moral judgment and moral injury. The study highlights cultural aspects of moral decision-making, such as moral segmentation in Hispanic contexts, which have been underexplored in medical training research. Also, it provides an important foundation for understanding moral injury in medical trainees, particularly in Latin America. While the findings are preliminary, they underscore the urgent need for more extensive research and institutional changes to equip future physicians to handle ethical dilemmas better.

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Contribution

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